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Designing SHM system using laser vibrometer-based sensor synthesis

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About GENEX

Problem description

- Sensor placement strategy that yields maximum damage detectability in the selected Region of Interest (ROI).
- Guided waves to be used for monitoring of planar and L-bent structures.
- Macro-fiber composites (MFC) sensors used (Smart Material Corp) due to their flexibility and ease of integration with the structure.
- Strategy involves placement of sensors around the ROI.

Characterization of the sample

- CFRP specimen representing real structure investigated experimentally.
- Specimens: baseline and sample with two artificial defects.
- Determine anisotropy, attenuation, and sensitivity of Lamb modes to defects.
- Lamb waves excited using PZT disc, responses measured using PSV-500 SLDV.
- Excitation using frequency sweep between 40 and 500 kHz, 1 ms duration.
- Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) increased using pulse-compression.

Stacking Sequence 21 plies:

(45/-45/0/-45/45/90/-45/45/45/-45/90/T/-45/45/45/-45/90/45/-45/0/-45/45)

Measured wavefield

Dispersion curves

- Dispersion curves calculated using 3D Fourier Transform of the full-field measurement.
- Modes A0 and S0 visible in the f-K spectrum.
- Mode A0 with slight anisotropy, mode S0 with significant anisotropy.
- Usable frequencies up to 220 – 250 kHz. Higher frequencies limited due to attenuation.

Defect properties - scattering

- wavefield snapshots

Telfon inserts

- incident wave filtered (reflections only)

Defect properties – local wavenumber

- To determine the influence of defects on Lamb waves, **local wavenumber estimation (LWE)** is used.
- LWE assumes filtering the space-time wavefield to retain a single Lamb mode at a selected frequency.
- The resulting 2D map shows distribution of local wavenumber.
- Higher wavenumber values visible at the location of defect.
- Background wavenumber values irregular – result from inhomogeneity of the plate.

Sensor network selection

- Properties of the plate and the defect lead to the use of **pitch-catch** sensor configuration.
- Due to inhomogeneity and anisotropy of the plate, sensor placement was determined using experimental analysis.
- To reduce the material usage, the analysis can be streamlined using virtualisation.
- **Artificial defect** and **virtual sensor** can be used to determine the best placement of physical transducers in the pitch-catch configuration.
- **Virtual sensor** involves representing the properties of the physical transducer using measurements with Scanning Laser-Doppler Vibrometer.
- **Artificial defect** involves substituting the real defect with added material that represents properties of a real defect.

physical setup

virtual setup

Artificial defect

- Typically, defects can be introduced into the sample during layup or by impact.
- To preserve the sample, the distortions to the wavefield can be obtained by adding material.
- In this work, a paste with abrasives is added on top of the sample.
- The LWE of the area with the paste compares well with the wavenumber of a damaged region.

- delamination

wavenumber map, v_1 , $f_c = 120$ kHz

- paste

wavenumber map, v_2 , $f_c = 120$ kHz

— damage v_1 - - - paste v_2 — — — undamaged v_1 - - - undamaged v_2

local wavenumber values

radius = 25 mm
height = 3 mm

Virtual sensor

- To obtain the properties of a physical MFC transducer using SLDV, a following virtualisation procedure is applied.
- Procedure assigns directivity pattern of the MFC transducer to $D(x, y, t)$.

Measurement series

- Investigation involves a **single MFC emitter** and **9 possible damage locations** within a quarter of assumed hot spot.
- Assumed four artificial defect sizes: 10, 15, 20 and 25 mm.
- For each damage location, 4 baselines were collected (one in the beginning and then one after every three damage locations).
- Scan grid consisted of 2121 points, excitation signal bandwidth 80-120 kHz.
- In this work: consider placement of a **single transducer**.

Locations:

Sizes:

Baseline 1 – Paste D25

Baseline 1 – Baseline 4

Sensor placement criterion

- Responses acquired from baseline $D_{base}(x, y, t)$ and a structure with added **artificial damage** $D_{dam}(x, y, t)$ are processed to determine most suitable sensor placement.
- Each dataset is processed using virtual transducer algorithm and the response for every x coordinate is obtained.
- Virtual transducer responses $V_{base}(x, t)$ and $V_{dam}(x, t)$ are used to calculate damage indices $DI(x)$ for all locations x .
- Highest values of $DI(x)$ correspond to desired transducer locations.

$$DI(x) = \sum_t (V_{dam}(x, t)^2 - V_{base}(x, t)^2)$$

Damage indices

Locations:

DIs for damage 25 x 25 mm

DIs for damage 20 x 20 mm

DIs for damage 15 x 15 mm

DIs for damage 10 x 10 mm

$$TH(x) = \overline{DI}_{base}(x) + 3 \cdot STD(DI_{base}(x))$$

- $\overline{DI}_{base}(x)$ – averaged DI from baselines
- STD – standard deviation from DIs

Validation

- pitch-catch measurement repeated for different plates (**Sample 1** and **Sample 2**)
- dX** equals 75 mm, similar distance **Y** between emitters and receivers
- artificial defects with radius 15 mm in locations 1-9
- DI values calculated for defects 1-9 and mapped onto image coordinates

Sample 1

- transmission between MFC transducers 3 and 6 – 4 positives

Sample 2

- reception between MFC and virtual sensor (VS) – 5 positives

Conclusions and future works

Conclusions

- outlined experimental procedure for SHM inspection of CFRP specimens
- virtual sensors and artificial defects enable designing the transducer array based on full-field measurements
- procedure validated for a simple pitch-catch setup

Future works

- generalize the framework for different SHM configurations by using non-contact excitation
- expand virtual transducers for different guided waves modes (e.g. using 3D vibration sensors)
- embed transducer properties in the excitation source
- more systematic investigation into artificial defects – modelling and manufacturing custom additives

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Characterization of the MFCs

MFC M0714P2

MFC M2807P2

Attenuation

- Attenuation estimated for line scans at orientations 0, 45 and 90 degrees.
- Mode A0 isolated using frequency – wavenumber filter.
- Curve-fitting to the exponential decay formula for different frequencies.
- Attenuation curve smoothed with moving average filter (n = 7).

$$v(r, f) = v(r_0, f) \sqrt{\frac{r_0}{r}} e^{-\alpha(f)(r-r_0)}$$

r – distance from the source

$A(r)$ – amplitude at r

α – attenuation coefficient

Fullfield imaging

